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IOT Based Food Safety System Real Time Monitoring for Optimal Storage

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ABSTRACT

This project focuses on developing a food safety system that continuously monitors storage conditions in real time to maintain food quality and its safety. Sensors are used to continuously measure important parameters such as temperature, humidity and air quality inside storage areas like cold rooms, refrigerators or warehouses. The collected data is sent to cloud-based platform or mobile application, where it is analyzed quickly. If any condition crosses the safe limit, the system sends alert to users so they can take action. This real time monitoring helps to prevent food spoilage, reduce waste, ensure safety standards and protect public health.

Keywords:- IOT, Cloud Computing, ESP32, Mobile Application, DHT Sensor, FECS Sensor

INTRODUCTION

Food safety is very important in our daily life. If food is not stored properly, it can get spoiled and may cause health problems. Factors like temperature, humidity and air quality play a major role in maintaining food quality. In many storage areas, food spoilage happens due to poor monitoring and lack of timely control.

With the advancement of technology, the Internet of Things (IoT) provides a smart solution for food storage. IoT allows sensors and devices to work together and share data in real time. In an IoT-based food safety and optimal storage system, sensors are used to continuously monitor storage conditions such as temperature, humidity and air quality.

The collected data is processed by a central controller, which automatically controls devices like exhaust fans and windows to maintain safe conditions. This reduces human effort, improves food quality, and minimizes food wastage. The proposed system is simple, cost-effective and suitable for warehouses, cold storage units and food processing industries.

LITERATURE SURVEY/REVIEW

Many studies have been done to improve food safety and storage methods. Earlier, food was stored using traditional methods Like refrigeration and manual checking. These methods help, but they do not always detect problems on time. Because of this, food often gets spoiled without anyone noticing.

Recent research shows that IoT technology can improve food storage systems. In many studies, researchers used temperature and humidity sensors to monitor food storage conditions. Some studies also used air quality sensors to keep the storage environment clean and safe. Researchers found that when sensors continuously monitor storage conditions and send data to a controller, food safety improves.

METHODOLOGY

This system works by continuously monitoring the storage environment. Process:

1. Different sensors are placed inside food storage area. These sensors measure factors like temperature, humidity and air quality. The sensors will send collected data to the controller through IoT. Controller compares the value and if it goes high than the limit then system takes immediate action. Based on sensor reading actuators like exhaust fans and automatic windows are turned ON or OFF. This will help in controlling heat, moisture inside storage area. All data is sent to cloud that user can monitor system using mobile.

CONTENT

Food storage means keeping food in the right way so that it stays fresh, safe, and good to eat for a longer time. If we stored food properly for ex.in clean, sealed containers, in a cool place, or inside the refrigerator at the correct temperature it does not go bad quickly and harmful bacteria cannot grow in it. This helps to avoid food waste, save money and stay healthy.

Focus	Scope
Artificial Intelligence	Cloud Computing and Applications
Food safety monitoring	Temperature, humidity, gas, detection
Optimal storage	Reduced spoilage.

RESEARCH AND REVIEWS

Keeping food safe and fresh is very important, especially in places like stores and kitchens. This system uses small electronic sensors that continuously measure conditions like temperature, humidity, gases. These sensors send data wirelessly to a server or cloud in real time.

RESULTS

The sensors check temperature, humidity and gas levels in real time. They collect data from sensors and send it to the cloud. The dashboard displayed live reading in the form of graphs or numbers. When the temperature or humidity crossed the safe limit, the system sent an alert message immediately and take any required action as per condition. The system works continuously.

DISCUSSION

The system reduces human power and saves time. The system gives immediately alert if any defect present in the food storage which helps to prevent food spoilage. It also improves food safety, quality and reduces food waste. The system totally depends on internet connection. if the network fails, then the transmission of data temporarily stopped.

CONCLUSION

The system continuously checks condition of food and also checks environment of food storage like temperature and humidity. We can use sensors here to collect data and sends it to the cloud. If there is any issue present in the food storage system then the system gives an alert immediately. This helps to keep food fresh, reduce waste, and improve safety.

FUTURE SCOPE

Artificial Intelligence (AI):
The system can detect food spoilage before it happens.

Automatic Temperature Control:
There is automatically adjusting cooling objects like exhaust fan.

Mobile App:
Using mobile apps, we can manage the system from anywhere.

Use in Transportation:
The system can be used in trucks for delivering food to the long distance.

More Advanced Sensors:
New sensors can detect bacteria, gas levels, and food freshness more.

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